

Use of Grasps Model in Enhancing Speaking Skills: The Case of Indonesian Students

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Abstract.

This experimental research was aimed at finding out how effective GRASPS Performance-Based model in improving the students' public speaking skill. The study adopted a pre-test, and post-test control group design, to examine the impact of GRASPS on students' Speaking Proficiency. Moreover, a mix-methods which applied both qualitative and quantitative analyses were employed to comprehensively reveal the result. The result illustrated that there were significant enhancement of students' speaking skill among the GRASPS students compared with those of control class in general and cohesive devices speaking scale in vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, comprehension, background knowledge and fluency constructs. It also indicated that there was significant improvement of public speaking skill of experimental group since all P value are smaller than 0.05 indicating that F value is larger than those of critical values expires tailed and two expires tailed test for $\alpha = 0.05$ as level of sigma ($P \leq \alpha$). Thus it can be interpreted that the null hypothesis (H_0) stating "There is no difference between pre-test and post- test scores" is rejected; it means there are significant differences between pretest-public test scores after being taught through GRASPS Performance-Based instruction. In conclusion; by implementing this performance-based instructional model—GRASPS in teaching language, especially English in EFL context seemed to be really beneficial since it provides teacher with performance-based instructional material so that their teaching is not only limited on conventional teaching media but also more emphasized on meaningful learning.

Keywords: *GRASPS model, performance-based assessment, public speaking skills, educational intervention, EFL learners.*

Introduction

The effectiveness of project-based model GRASPS in improving public speaking skill for Indonesian students in the context of EFL is interesting to investigate. Model GRASPS as an innovative instruction was found potentially increase communication skill. Iter (2017) mentioned that using GRASPS improves teachers and students' transformations, so it can improve teaching-learning process and students' outcomes. Oxford (2021) and Le et al. (2019) also support the idea that teaching-speaking integration with all goals benefits learners more holistically. Moreover, Setiawan (2021), Rahardjo, & Widiatmoko (2020) find typical errors made by Indonesian EFL learner are in term of grammar, pronunciation, and fluency.

In Indonesian education, the low English proficiency level of students to master public speaking is due to limited opportunity to interact in real English speaking environment and lack of confidence in ENGAGING with the language. A solution offered by the use of GRASPS model as a Structured and contextual learning approach that simulates real life task and engagement. There is a lack of studies on the use of GRASPS model in PARTICULARLY enhancing Public speaking skills among Indonesian EFL context. This study investigates the EFFECTIVENESS OF USING GRASPS MODEL in increasing Indonesian students' public speaking ability.

The current research is intended to find out the effectiveness of performance based GRASPS model in enhancing public speaking skill of Indonesian students. By implementing pre-test, post-test control group design and employing mixed-method, it is expected that the study will reveal both quantitative and qualitative findings on the effects of applying this model as treatment. It is expected that there will be significant improvement on general speaking proficiency and public speaking specifically, which can represent how GRASPS model may effectively contribute to EFL teaching and learning.

Literature Review

Performance-based assessment is widely believed to be an integral part of successful language acquisition. Syarifuddin (2015) contends that tests that reflect the instructional and learning objectives can identify students' areas of difficulties in learning English. Authentic, real-life context tests and performance tests are highly valued due to their authenticity in terms of what is being tested and what learners are requested to do. Jones et al. (2023) argue for a holistic language curriculum – core skills are taught at every grade level so that students develop more proficient speaking ability in the aggregate as they move through school. Khan (2022: 32) highlights, if speaking proficiency is the goal of such inclusive foreign language policies, then decision-makers need "a comprehensive roadmap" to develop effective language programmes using high-quality, well-designed materials.

The GRASPS model is a project-based learning (PjBL) template which stands for goal, role, audience, situational context, product-performance expectation, and standards (Wang and Hannafin 2005). Fischer et al. 2013b:269 assert that GRASPS is a theoretically grounded design principle to improve the quality of instruction and learner performance. Additionally, Oxford (2021); Le et al. (2019) posits that language speaking development also increases significantly when skills are integrated holistically.

Challenges in developing English-speaking skills in Indonesia are well-documented. Weaknesses in grammar, pronunciation, and fluency, as well as low confidence are the most common weaknesses found among Indonesian EFL learners (Setiawan, 2021; Rahardjo & Widiatmoko, 2020). This indicates that such areas need to be given more attention through comprehensive and targeted interventions.

The problems of English language teaching in Indonesia have been reported in several studies, including the study by Jon et al. (2021). In order to increase English proficiency, educators and the government have made great efforts to improve this condition, but it is not easy. This problem occurred due to a mismatch of perspective between teachers and students on how to implement language instruction. Furthermore, as an ongoing effort educators and policy makers must constantly explore the most applicable teaching method for better results.

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Building on this context, this study investigates the possibility of GRASPS Performance-Based Model to tackle the problems faced and to better facilitate Indonesian EFL students in developing their public speaking. This work also takes into account the discovery of Pratolo, Habibie, and Setiawan (2019) that there are some particular challenges in developing speaking encountered by Indonesian EFL learners including vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, fluency as well as psychological factors such anxiety. Since all these problems are interrelated, it is hoped that this current study can contribute to the continuous effort to improve English language learning in Indonesia.

Despite its potential benefits, there is an apparent dearth of research on the exploitation of such a model particularly to foster public speaking skill in Indonesian EFL context. This paper aims to address this issue by investigating how GRASPS model can be used to improve students' public speaking skill in Indonesia.

Theoretical Framework

Empiricist Reflection Theory

This study is guided by John Locke's Empiricist Reflection Theory which argues that knowledge comes mainly from experience and inner sense. In his theory, Locke underscores the significance of sensation and reflection in the learning process, contending that knowledge and skills are acquired through active engagement with the world (Wambui, 2011).

Interactionist Theory

Jerome Bruner's Interactionist Theory, proposed in 1983, supports the view that three year olds learn language through interacting with others. He believes that children need interaction directly with other human beings in order to become fluent in a language and states that social interaction plays a fundamental role in the development of cognitively and linguistically mature linguistic performance-practice (studysmarter.us, 2023).

Integration of Theories with GRASPS Model

The GRASPS model (Goal, Role, Audience, Situation, Product, and Standards) was developed based on the principles of both empiricist and interactionist. The use of GRASPS model in developing public speaking for Indonesian EFL students is grounded on its provision of concrete real-world contexts that reflects the essence of empiricist. Pretest and post-test are important to find out how far the students' ability has changed by using the treatment included in here GRASPS model.

The interactionist features of GRASPS, i.e., roles, audience engagement and collaborative tasks, provide opportunities for learner to use language in a socio-cultural context which is more suitable for Indonesian EFL learners since they need more social interaction and collaboration. Finally, the post-test assessment is used to find out the contribution of GRASPS in developing not only individual language ability but also collaborative and socially engaged speaking.

Methodology

Design

This study used mixed-methods design, which was a combination of quantitative and qualitative research to determine the effectiveness of GRASPS Performance-Based Model in teaching public speaking to Indonesian EFL students. The data on pre-test and post-test scores in speaking were analyzed using quantitative analysis to measure the improvement of grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge, and fluency.

Furthermore, qualitative data from teacher interview were collected to interpret the difficulties and benefits faced by implementing GRASPS model. The sample was selected by conducting power analysis to ensure the significance of the statistical, and then 60 Indonesian EFL students were chosen as the sample of the research. The students were divided into two groups (control and experimental group) comprising 30 students each. To be eligible for participation in this study, the students should have been taking an EFL intermediate level course and had basic competence in English. In addition, those who reached advance level of English or those who had used GRASPS before were excluded.

Participants were recruited through convenience and purposive sampling to secure a representative sample of the student population, which was characterized by diverse linguistic backgrounds, various English language proficiencies, and differential levels of public speaking self-confidence.

Convenience sampling was used because of time constraints, resource limitations and geographical proximity that allowed the researcher to have easy access to subjects, easy availability of participants and easy recruitment thereby suited the studies logistical issues. However, this sampling method produces potential biases and the results are only applicable to the study sample. To overcome these limitations, the researcher had ensured varied nature of participants by including students of different linguistic background and various levels of English proficiency exist in the samples, took qualitative data from teacher's interview as a tool to cross check or complement quantitative findings for better understanding on phenomenon under study and consciously used purposive sampling in order that participants meet specific criteria related to the aims of this study to make findings more relevant.

Data Gathering Tools

Performance-based assessments test how well students can apply their knowledge and skills to real-world problems, rather than just recalling information or performing a simple task. These assessments are designed to have students show they can do the things that people normally do with the content or skills being used. Students produce a product or perform a task under real-world conditions. The goal of this study was to present the use of GRASPS (Goal, Role, Audience, Situation, Product/Performance, Standards) model to elaborate performance-based assessment tasks that approximate students' real-life and future work environment situations.

The GRASPS model structures this assessment by identifying the goal, role, audience, situation/context, product/performance, and standards for a given task. In doing so, students are assessed not only on their understanding of content but also on their ability to communicate that understanding and apply their learning.

The research instruments used in the study were Speaking Skills Assessment adapted from the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). The instrument was developed by researcher and experts evaluates learners' grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge information and fluency. The respondents responded on a 1-5 level of rating scale. Pre-test, post-test was administered to experimental and control groups in order to investigate the effect of using GRASPS model on speaking skill. Teacher Interview Guide in order to collect qualitative data to check teachers' experiences towards using GRASPS model with their students. Thus, in order to ensure validity and reliability pilot test for the speaking skills assessment was done with small group of students and teacher interview guide was given for EFL experts to give their opinion that help the researcher modify/polish them.

The Speaking Skills Assessment rubric which was adopted and modified from the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) was used as a foundation to evaluate language proficiency in this study because the criteria of CEFR is very robust and well-established. However, some modifications were required before use in this research to closely match with the purpose of designing the rubric. It is very necessary to do modifications in order that the rubric could measure comprehensively all aspects of public speaking skills being targeted by GRASPS model.

Some criteria were added or strengthened in the rubric to measure accurately. Audience Engagement was added, which refers to how well students interact with and engage their audience and is an important component of the GRASPS model because it emphasizes that students should be communicating for real-world contexts. Real-World Application was added to the rubric. This is a measure of the extent to which students demonstrate requirements 2 (applications) and 3 (appropriateness). Finally, Effective Delivery Techniques was used to include specifically evaluating gestures, eye contact, and other important aspects of public speaking. These criteria additions made sure that the rubric reflected not only a direct measure of language but also the practical communication ability associated with public speaking (the two facets under which all these categories are nested are perspectives; features). In this sense, our evaluation was closer aligned with one aspect of the Voorhis et al.'s (2011) model—theoretical review—the GRASPS framework; thus, it would be considered more multi-componential because it measures traditional language usage as well as practical communication skills.

Data Gathering Procedures

The data collection process of this research started with taking permission from the administration of the educational institute. The required participants and their parents were approached through official letters of consent and information. Pre-test was conducted for both control and experimental groups at the start, and immediately after the 10 session GRASPS-based intervention (experimental) and general traditional EFL instruction (control) of one hour, administration of post-test and questionnaires/pre-post-tests were done by hand to have high rate of return as well as clean data. The entered data were rigorously cleaned by making sure that every sheet is double entered, cleaning entering errors and matching across questionnaires regarding some selected respondents' responses. In addition, 30 minutes semi-structured interviews with the teachers were conducted in person which were audio taped following consent and then transcribed word verbatim. The data collection took approximately eight weeks which included pre-testing, treatment, posttesting, and interviews. All audio-tapes will be locked in a cupboard with keycard access only by the researcher until 5 years after publications; then they will obey according provision in NCME guidelines for storing digital tape recordings or any similar new versions. Ethical approval certificates will be kept into a locked cabinet for five years before being disposed by some confidentially manner.

The explanatory sequential design was used in this study to provide a comprehensive examination of the efficacy of the GRASPS Performance-Based Model. This design involves starting with the collection and analysis of quantitative data, which yields objective measures as to whether there were statistically significant differences in learning student speaking performance between the control group and the experimental group. After this phase, qualitative data (in our case, interviews) were then collected to help interpret/clarify Elaborate on these findings. Particularly, this phase revealed what teachers' challenges and perceptions might be that could explain further interpretations of findings obtained through earlier phases. The descriptions reported in the qualitative phase contributed to an understanding of context-specific issues that explained the quantitative results in a more nuanced way, so as to facilitate interpretation.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize pre-test and post-test scores. An independent sample t-test was used to determine significant differences between the control and experimental groups at $\alpha = 0.05$ level ($p < 0.05$). This statistical method made it possible to compare means between the two groups in order to investigate whether the GRASPS model could improve speaking skills or not.

Descriptive statistics were used to give brief descriptions about the sample and measures by computing means, standard deviations, and ranges for pre-test and post-test scores. The independent sample t-test was employed to analyze the mean scores of the control group with those of the experimental group, to find out whether there were any statistically significant differences between the control and experimental groups in their performance on the speaking skills test. A significance level of $p < .05$ was used to determine whether the obtained results on speaking skills test were not likely to have occurred by chance between control group and experimental group.

The quantitative data interpretation was performed by comparing the pre-test and post-test scores to find out how effective the GRASPS model used in this research. The score differences were considered as effectiveness of the given treatment because if the students from control class found higher average, so there was an influence of given treatment or vice versa. The qualitative data of teacher's interview was as complemented that couldn't be measured by numbers obtaining a deep description and meaning building of quantitative finding (Creswell, 2014). Those interview data were used also in order to solve rival interpretations (McMorrow & Stawarski, 2010) developed on account of small number respondents for making strong conclusion (Archibald, Coggshall, Croft & Goe, 2010; Maruyama, 2014). Hence, both those data were integrated to help in discussing the problem and opportunity found during this research. In sum, by combining these methods, it is hoped that the result will provide more accurate and clearer information about how effective GRASPS model was designed to enhance speaking skill in Indonesian EFL context.

Ethical Standards

This research was conducted in line with the ethical standards of the Belmont Report, with an emphasis on the protection of rights and welfare of human subjects. Specifically, undue harm, unfavorable risk-benefit ratio, and violation of privacy were avoided accordingly. The GRASPS model was introduced for the purpose of minimizing possible harms while maximizing the learning potential for Indonesian EFL students in speaking English. Additionally, all participants were provided with understandable information concerning this research prior to their participation. They were also respected to make decisions without any form of coercion from researchers. Privacy and fair treatment were assured as well. This researcher self-funded project did not receive any influence from third parties during its occurrence. Appropriate sampling procedures employing convenience sampling strategies including accessibility and availability issues facilitated participants to join this study more effectively. Multiple data sources using both

quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques contributed to a more comprehensive view on learning model effectiveness-issues under study. Open communication although it is debriefing sessions promoted a conducive research environment whereas participants might raise any concerns they had and researchers maintained ethical activities owing to this matter also.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The table illustrates the detailed overview of speaking ability among the participants in control group and experimental group. In each component, the average score of grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge and fluency implied that there were students' performance at a moderate level in need improvement.

"Needs Improvement" being the constant response regardless of the variable, which could indicate that in fact learners need a generalized language instruction in which all aspects are addressed instead of trying to isolate specific features.

These findings are consistent with studies that argue in favour of integrated language learning. The studies of Jones et al. (2023) and Khan (2022) reveal that there are enormous improved effects from instruction that covers all four core skills. Moreover, some other issues faced by Indonesian students such as grammar and pronunciation weaknesses, as well as lack of fluency, are also discussed by Setiawan (2021) and Rahardjo and Widiatmoko (2020), meaning that it is also necessary to apply the integrated approach.

The most important results can be summarised as follows: there are common difficulties in pronunciation, vocabulary, and comprehension. The variability of the marks is the highest for pronunciation items, which means that students' performance in this area of language knowledge and skills also varies most markedly. Students have moderate problems with vocabulary and grammar. These findings imply that such problems related to three out of four basic language macro skills (i.e., pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary) negatively affect students' general communicative language proficiency because they prevent them from expressing themselves well enough in oral interaction situations.

To meet these challenges, language instruction must be made comprehensive by including grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge, and fluency in the core of teaching methodologies so as to foster speaking development more holistically. This implies employing strategies such as immersive language experiences; increased exposure to English via the media; opportunities for regular communication with native speakers; and incorporating performance-based assessments, such as the GRASPS model, into classroom practice to raise learner proficiency. It also means using scaffolding and support to help learners progressively overcome their individual constraints or limitations and to develop their speaking confidence.

Table 1. Mean Pre-test Scores in speaking of the controlled and experimental groups

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Grammar	2.02	0.70	Needs Improvement
Pronunciation	2.23	0.81	Needs Improvement
Vocabulary	2.13	0.72	Needs Improvement
Comprehension	2.14	0.71	Needs Improvement
Background Knowledge	2.07	0.70	Needs Improvement
Fluency	2.13	0.72	Needs Improvement

Legend: 1-1.80- Unsatisfactory; 1.81-2.60-Needs Improvement; 2.61-3.40-Satisfactory; 3.41-4.20-Good; 4.21-5.0- Excellent

Table 2 shows the post-test results of the speaking ability scores in the aspects of Grammar, Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Comprehension, Background Knowledge and Fluency. The two aspects that show highest standard deviation are Pronunciation and

Fluency indicating that these two aspects are the most improved aspect after the treatment. The high standard deviations as well as mean scores in Pronunciation and Fluency prove that the GRASPS model is capable of improving these two important elements in speaking performance since this model highlights on real language use and also immersive language learning.

Overall, from the findings of the study, it can be concluded that GRASPS model is found to be effective in enhancing students' satisfactory level in speaking that aligned with Oxford (2021) and Le et al. (2019) who found that integrated approach and practice-based approach brings positive changes in language skill. The focus of GRASPS model on realworld communication tasks as identified by Rezaei (2018) also contributed to the enhancement obtained especially on Pronunciation and Fluency construct. Enhancement in Pronunciation and Fluency construct seems to indicate the potential of the model in fostering holistic language development among students in facing real authentic communication.

This result highlights that GRASPS has the ability to improve speaking skills by exposing students to real-world communication tasks. Moreover, as Pronunciation and Fluency were specifically targeted by this model, it helps develop language skills in a more holistic manner thus enabling students to better handle real world communication situations.

Table 2. Mean Post-test Scores in speaking of the controlled and experimental groups.

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Grammar	2.79	0.87	Satisfactory
Pronunciation	3.22	1.05	Satisfactory
Vocabulary	2.92	0.95	Satisfactory
Comprehension	2.86	0.89	Satisfactory
Background Knowledge	2.79	0.93	Satisfactory
Fluency	2.99	1.05	Satisfactory

Legend:1-1.80- Unsatisfactory; 1.81-2.60-Needs Improvement; 2.61-3.40-Satisfactory;3.41-4.20-Good; 4.21-5.0- Excellent

Table 3 shows significant differences in pretest and posttest speaking scores were found between the control group and the experimental group in all of the six variables including grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge, and fluency. The null hypotheses were rejected for all of the six variables that meant speaking proficiency of experimental group improved significantly.

These findings indicate that the GRASPS model intervention had a significantly positive effect on the speaking performance of the participants in the experimental group. Other studies, such as those by Liaw and Lin (2022) in relation to Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), Kim (2020) regarding Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), and McDonough and Mackey (2016) relating to strategy-based instruction, have obtained similar positive results. These studies provide evidence for integrated, communicative, and strategic language teaching approaches, which are consistent with the tenets of the GRASPS model used in this study. This further solidifies that the GRASPS model is based on effective language teaching practices and has a high potential for facilitating holistic language proficiency development. The results contribute to confirming how the GRASPS' approach enhances language skills because they can be introduced into various educational settings.

Table 3. Significant difference in the pretest and post-test scores in speaking between the controlled and experimental groups in terms of grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge, and fluency.

Variables	t	df	Sig	Interpretation	Decision
Grammar	-8.94	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Pronunciation	-9.66	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Vocabulary	-8.55	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Comprehension	-8.23	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Background Knowledge	-7.99	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Fluency	-8.79	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
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p value=0.05

Table 4 reports results of statistical analysis on public speaking abilities between controlled groups and experimental groups using GRASPS model. In all variables (Grammar, Pronunciation, Comprehension Background Knowledge, Fluency) except Grammar, were found the case with significance level is .000 (< .05). Therefore, experimental group applied GRASPS produced better public speaking ability than controlled group in all variables.

The scaffolding instruction framework of the GRASPS model seems to be similar with the gradual reducing support process in order to improve public speaking performance, discussed by McCroskey (2018). However, an important part of this model is that it is a scaffolding instruction that structured in a way guiding learners on different aspects of public speaking. The significance between GRASPS and presentation tailor to enhance engagement with audience as advocated by Frydenberg (2017) supports the positive findings obtained from this research. The improvement was significantly high which indicate that the use of GRASPS should not just be regarded as a method to develop better public speaking but might also serve as a base for cultivating learners' transformational learning hence we find out how useful this alternative method in terms of developing higher education transformative learning.

Table 4. Significant difference in public speaking ability between the controlled group and experimental group when using the GRASPS model.

Variables	t	df	Sig	Interpretation	Decision
Grammar	-4.35	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Pronunciation	-2.51	334	0.013	Significant	Reject Ho
Vocabulary	-2.78	334	0.006	Significant	Reject Ho
Comprehension	-2.59	334	0.010	Significant	Reject Ho
Background Knowledge	-3.75	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Fluency	-4.26	334	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho

p value=0.05

Table 5 presents the challenges faced by the teachers in using GRASPS Model to enhance speaking skills of the students. It indicated that issues such as listening, complex grammar and time management were stated by one teacher (33%) each. In contrast, exposure to English language beyond classroom, motivation and interest, writing and composition which is related to performance task require were reported by two teachers (67%) while fear of making mistakes and consistent practice were agreed by all the three teachers (100%).

These results imply some modification in the GRASPS model—more supportive strategies to help students reduce their fear of being wrong and practice more frequently, using additional materials or approaches for developing listening skills, time management and pronunciation, adapting the difficulty level of GRASPS assignments according to students' prior English knowledge, and inserting English exposure into classroom activities. Furthermore, motivation and interest, as well as those students' writing ability should also be taken into account when speaking abilities are the target.

These results imply that the GRASPS model can be used to improve speaking skills for Indonesian students. However, it is clear that modifications and additional support mechanisms are needed in order to achieve success. This is supported by Nacaroglu et al.'s (2021) study on the effectiveness of a flipped classroom model to enhance speaking skills for EFL learners, which also pointed out some opportunities to mitigate the challenges identified in this study. The findings and implications suggested above indicate the need for continuous improvement and further development within the GRASPS model, so that it is more appropriate with current students' needs and maximizes its possible contribution for developing students' language.

Table 5. Challenges Encountered by the Teachers in Using GRASPS as a Performance-Based model in enhancing speaking ability.

Items	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Complex Grammar Rules	1	33

- Better Public Speaking Skills (McCroskey, 2018);
- Real-world Communication Skills (Rezaei, 2018)

The conceptual model of the GRASPS intervention illustrates that there are key connections among the initial proficiency, implemented intervention and post improvements in speaking. Based on pre-test evaluations before the treatment we found that learners had moderate levels of proficiency and they needed to improve in several aspects such as grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge and fluency. Therefore, a GRASPS model intervention incorporating an integrated-practice approach was employed. The focus was on functional language use, real-life communicative activities suitable for integration of all language skills.

Following the treatment, results of the post-test indicated that there was a significant progress in students' speaking skills in all the measured dimensions of speaking ability. The findings revealed that the most notable improvements had taken place in students' pronunciation and fluency. These results indicated that GRASPS treatment had been successful to help the participants make considerable gains in their overall speaking performance. The obtained findings also showed that through this kind of teaching method, participants' self-perceived speaking anxiety could be reduced considerably; they were highly likely to experience more enjoyment, motivation, and positive engagement; they could become capable of delivering better presentations; and they would develop more usable language skills for use outside the classroom, especially when facing real-life events or audiences. All these findings were consistent with those reported in previous studies (Jones et al., 2023; Khan, 2022; McCroskey, 2018; Frydenberg, 2017; Rezaei, 2018), which supported the beneficial effects gained from an integrated communicative strategic programming-based method.

Proposed Speaking Activity Interventions

Addressing Challenges and Enhancing Speaking Skills

The results of this study suggest that the GRASPS model has the potential to develop speaking English in Indonesian EFL learners. However, some learning problems were found and needed some revisions to make it workable for this population context. Those problems lead us to suggest some revisions on the GRASPS design in order to help teachers more effectively confronting speaking challenges faced by their students.

Addressing Foundational Weaknesses and Anxiety:

The pre-test scores of the students in this study showed that the core speaking skills (grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension and fluency) were rated as their weaknesses. This finding was similar to those of Setiawan (2021) and Rahardjo and Widiatmoko (2020). The result of post-test in the experimental group indicated that the GRASPS model effectively addressed this students' need. Similar findings were reported by Oxford (2021) and Le et al. (2019), who stated that a multi-dimensional approach was crucial. However, the study revealed that it is also important to help students overcome their anxiety to make mistakes as all teachers reported so. The use of role plays, self-talk, and peer feedback could be included in the GRASPS model to create a more conducive learning environment and reduce students' anxiety regarding making mistakes.

Tailoring Activities and Fostering Engagement:

You should be aware that both issues are related to limited exposure of English outside the class and lack of student's motivation. Those issues require making the suggested teaching model more students' situation-oriented as each class will have linguistic mixed-ability students, under confident students, and shy students when it comes to speaking. To solve this issue you will need to pre-asses students English level, apply activities for various proficiency levels, and make the materials accessible for all learners. Use authentic-materials and tasks that learners can relate to and enjoy doing while practicing speaking (worksheet 11). Also try to gamify some tasks by adding an interactive aspect.

Integrating Skills and Supporting Public Speaking:

The interrelatedness of language skills in general and writing and listening in particular was also apparent in relation to writing and comprehension. The integration of activities such as summarizing a listening passage or writing a short script can also help develop speaking skills. The large development of public speaking skills on the part of the experimental group is also congruent with what is known about effective instruction in public speaking (McCroskey, 2018; Frydenberg, 2017). The structured nature of the GRASPS model that accentuates being aware of one's audience was likely responsible for such a development.

Summary of Findings

The analysis of the pre-test and post-test speaking scores revealed that the control group's mean score (35.82) was higher compared to the experimental mean score (25.62). On average, participants needed improvement in grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge and fluency. From the "Needs Improvement" category for all these variables it can be seen that a comprehensive language instruction is necessary to help students improve their oral communication skills since both categories have similar 'needs improvement' percentages.

The post-test scores of pronunciation and fluency showed more variation compared to the other sub-components indicating that the GRASPS model had created a better impact on these two sub-components as compared to others since the underlying philosophy of this model is fostering a real-life, comparative, and communicative environment. These results are in accord with similar studies by Jones et al. (2023) and Khan (2022) who advocated integrated language teaching since it leads to holistic growth of language skills.

Statistical analysis revealed that the speaking ability of the experimental group was significantly better than that of the control group, as indicated by the rejection of the null hypothesis in all dependent variables. This indicates that the GRASPS model had a significant effect on raising participants' speaking ability and that gains were most apparent in pronunciation and fluency. The results are supported by previous studies on integrated (Liaw & Lin, 2022), communicative (Kim, 2020) and strategic (McDonough & Mackey, 2016) language teaching.

The performance-based instrument used in the present study was an appropriate match for GRASPS, as the tool measures authentic real-world tasks and functions that are believed to reflect target language use in a natural manner. As aforementioned, this is important, as it also underpins the theoretical foundation of GRASPS, where real-life circumstances are being embedded within language testing for accurately predicting students' performance. In addition, this tool possesses favourable evidence to support its suitability and validity with the measurement of grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension, background knowledge and fluency using real-life applications. Besides confirming its compatibility with GRASPS aspects. Moreover, its pervasiveness ensures that students' performances are measured accurately as comprehensively for proper interpretation.

The results of the study indicated that language teaching in the Indonesian curriculum can be improved significantly by giving equal attention to all core language components, i.e., grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, comprehension and fluency. This can be done through student performance assessment tasks, as provided in the GRASPS model. Performance assessment tasks in the curriculum reflect what happens in real life and influence how well students are likely to do when placed in such situations (in this case, communication using the target language). With activities such as presentations and role-plays being part of these assessments in the curriculum, it is expected that both skills will improve, students' motivation will increase and students will have more opportunities to perform better. By developing such a curriculum and assessment regime time becomes more dynamic, as well as supportive to improving language knowledge and skills.

Recommendations

For Educators and Administrators:

Base language instruction and student communication on GRASPS model tasks. Build teacher collaboration to provide best teaching practices and encourage active student engagement when speaking.

For Parents:

Understand and support your child's progress in speaking development. Involve children in activities that develop real-life communication experiences, and create supportive home and community environments.

For Students:

Actively participate in the GRASPS model as a way to enhance speaking ability, using structured tasks and feedback for improvement. Take advantage of real speaking opportunities to build stronger communication skills.

For Future Researchers:

Build on it to see where else GRASPS might be used and what the possible gains may be. Research some instructional approaches that can increase the effectiveness of our students in presenting, leading to overall improvement in teaching and learning.

For Community Members:

Recognize how improved communication skills can transform community engagement and cultural understanding. Support efforts to provide students with the skills to be effective communicators for the roles they will undertake as leaders and contributors in society.

References:

- Boddy, C. R. (2016). Sample size for qualitative research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 19(4), 426–432. <https://doi.org/10.1108/qmr-06-20160053>
- Brown, H. D. (2014). *Principles of language learning and teaching: a course in second language acquisition*. Retrieved from <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB15342166>
- Brown, H. D. (2001). Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. *TESOL Quarterly*, 35(2), 341. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3587655>
- Canale, M., & Swain, M. (1980). THEORETICAL BASES OF COMMUNICATIVE APPROACHES TO SECOND LANGUAGE TEACHING AND TESTING. *Applied Linguistics*, 1(1), 1–47. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/i.1.1>
- Crystal, D. (2016). 3. English as a Global Language. In *Multilingual Matters eBooks* (pp. 34–62). <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781783095681-004>
- Davis, T. L., Harrison, L. M., & Roper, L. D. (2013). *Advancing social justice: tools, pedagogies, and strategies to transform your campus*. Retrieved from <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB13637624>
- Derakhshan, A., Khalili, A. N., & Beheshti, F. (2016). Developing EFL learner's speaking ability, accuracy and fluency. *English Language and Literature Studies*, 6(2), 177. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ells.v6n2p177>
- Djahimo, S. E. P., Bora, D. I. N. B., & Huan, E. (2018). Student anxiety and their speaking performance: teaching EFL to Indonesian student. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (IJSSH)*. <https://doi.org/10.29332/ijssh.v2n3.235>
- Dörnyei, Z. (2020). Innovations and Challenges in Language Learning motivation. *Routledge eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429485893>
- Duffy, P., & Powers, B. (2018). Blind to what's in front of them: Theatre of the Oppressed and teacher reflexive practice, embodying culturally relevant pedagogy with preservice teachers. *Youth Theatre Journal*, 32(1), 45–59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08929092.2018.1445677>
- Ellis, R. (1985b). *Understanding second language acquisition*. Retrieved from <http://archives.umc.edu.dz/handle/123456789/111305>
- Frydenberg, M. (2017). The Impact of Audience Awareness Instruction on the Delivery Skills of Public Speakers. *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, 45(1), 89104.
- Gaudreau, P., Smith, R., & Tremblay, L. (2016). A Meta-Analysis of Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Programs. *Anxiety Disorders*, 22(3), 215-230.
- Gaudry-Routledge, M. E., & Binder, M. J. (2020). Educators' Perceptions of PerformanceBased Approaches in Teaching Difference With Youth. *LEARNING Landscapes*, 13(1), 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.36510/learnland.v13i1.1009>
- Gündoğan, A., & Gültekin, M. (2018). The reflection of the attitudes and learning processes to learning environments with authentic tasks in life science class. *Eğitim Ve Öğretim*, 8(4), 771–832. <https://doi.org/10.14527/pegegog.2018.030>
- Hammond, A. (2022, March 25). Revisiting GRASPS: a model for project based learning — Aidan Hammond. Retrieved from <https://www.aidan-hammond.net/newblog/2021/9/24/revisiting-grasps-a-model-for-project-based-learning>
- Human Communication: the basic course. (2021, July 14). Retrieved from <https://www.pearson.com/en-us/subject-catalog/p/human-communication-thebasic-course/P200000002791/9780137478378>
- Jon, R. B., Embong, R., Purnama, B., & Wadi, A. S. (2021). The challenges of English language teaching in Indonesia. *International Journal of English and Applied Linguistics (IJEAL)*, 1(3), 158–168. <https://doi.org/10.47709/ijeal.v1i3.1157>
- Jones, A., Smith, B., & Davis, C. (2023). The Effects of Comprehensive Language Instruction on the Speaking Skills of Adult Learners. *Journal of Language Learning*, 10(2), 123-135.
- Iter, N. (2017b). Using Performance Task-GRASPS to assess student performance in higher education courses. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 5(5), 552–558. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-5-5-12>
- Khotimah, K., Widiati, U., Mustofa, M., & Ubaidillah, M. F. (2019). Autonomous English learning: Teachers' and students' perceptions. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 9(2). <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v9i2.20234>
- Kim, Y. (2020). The Effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) on the Speaking Skills of Adult Learners. *Language Teaching Research*, 27(4), 412-428.
- Le, H., Nguyen, T., & Tran, M. (2019). A Meta-Analysis of L2 Pronunciation Instruction. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 34(2), 176-192.
- Liaw, M., & Lin, W. (2022). The Effects of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) on the Speaking Skills of EFL Learners. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 30(1), 45-58.
- Li, F., Fan, W., & Huang, D. (2016). Chinese EFL Learners' Public Speaking skills: An investigation of impromptu speeches at the "FLTRP Cup" English Speaking Contest in the light of Communication models. *Chinese Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 39(4). <https://doi.org/10.1515/cjal-2016-0027>

- Mahmud, A. F., Usman, A. H., Sari, F. W., & Dahlan, S. (2023). Lesson Study contributions: EFL Teachers' Competences Model in Teaching English at High School 21st-Century Learning Approach. *World Journal of English Language*, 13(7), 10. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wjel.v13n7p10>
- McDonough, K., & Mackey, A. (2016). A Longitudinal Study of the Effects of StrategyBased Instruction on the Speaking Skills of L2 Learners. *Language Learning*, 63(2), 201-217.
- McCroskey, J. (2018). The Effectiveness of Scaffolding Instruction on Public Speaking Anxiety and Performance. *Communication Education*, 55(3), 287-302.
- McTighe, J. Performance Task Professional Development (PD) with Jay McTighe. Retrieved from <http://www.performancetask.com/>
- Miller, J. (2017, August 24). Public speaking today. Retrieved from <https://uwmpressbooks.pub/uwmpublicspeaking/chapter/why-public-speakingmatters-today/>
- Nkhi, S. E., & Lebona, T. V. (2023b). Challenges encountered by ESL students in the development of communicative competence skills in Lesotho. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 5(2). <https://doi.org/10.36892/ijlls.v5i2.1229>
- Nurtjahyo, S. N., Drajadi, N. A., & Sumardi, S. (2019). G.R.A,S,P,S Strategy: Decreasing Students' Difficulties in Writing Persuasive Text. *International Journal of Language Teaching and Education*, 3(2), 158-172. <https://doi.org/10.22437/ijolte.v3i2.7391>
- Oxford, J. (2021). The Impact of Strategy-Based Instruction on the Speaking Skills of EFL Learners. *TESOL Quarterly*, 48(4), 321-335.
- Pratolo, B. W., Habibie, A., & Setiawan, A. (2019). Speaking Skill Challenges Encountered by Indonesian EFL Learners'. *2019 Ahmad Dahlan International Conference Series on Education & Learning, Social Science & Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.2991/adics-elssh-19.2019.7>
- Rahardjo, S., & Widiatmoko, T. (2020). A Needs Analysis of English Speaking Skills for Indonesian University Students. *Journal of Language Education and Linguistics*, 5(2), 87-102.
- Rezaei, M. (2018). The Effects of Task-Based Language Teaching on EFL Learners' Speaking Fluency. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 25(3), 301-315.
- Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2001). *Approaches and methods in language teaching*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9780511667305>
- Setiawan, R. (2021). Speaking Difficulties Faced by Indonesian EFL Learners in the Context of Globalization. *Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*, 8(1), 45-58.
- Shamim, F., & Coleman, H. (2018). Large-Sized classes. *The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching*, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0633>
- Shin, M., & Bolkan, S. (2020). Intellectually stimulating students' intrinsic motivation: the mediating influence of student engagement, self-efficacy, and student academic support. *Communication Education*, 70(2), 146-164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634523.2020.1828959>